

Strategic Communication as an Innovative Instrument for Climate adaptation and Mitigation in Africa

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Abstract

This article explored the vital role of communication in driving Africa's efforts to adapt to and mitigate climate change. By adopting a positional and analytical approach to analyse data from academic studies, policy documents, media reports and collaborations with NGOs, the study explored examples from Senegal, Uganda, Kenya and Somalia to illustrate its findings. The research emphasised the importance of inclusion, dialogue and shared knowledge by using development communication and participatory action research as a framework. Various communication tools, such as community radio, mobile platforms, traditional oral systems and youth-led digital initiatives, were examined for their ability to spread climate-related information, influence behaviours and shape policy discussions. The findings revealed that these tools strengthen mitigation by fostering awareness and engagement. However, challenges like institutional neglect, cultural and language barriers, and limited resources hinder their full potential. Despite these obstacles, the study identifies instances where effective communication has led to behavioural shifts, increased civic participation and meaningful policy changes. Therefore, it is concluded that communication is not a secondary element but a central driver of climate action in Africa. Among others, it recommends integrating communication strategies into national climate policies and prioritising investments in community-based and digital innovations to ensure inclusive and sustainable responses to climate challenges.

Keywords: Climate Adaptation, Climate Mitigation, Strategic Communication, Africa, Information

Introduction

It is arguable that Africa continues to be one of the most climate-vulnerable regions on a global scale. Its economies, ecosystems and human populations are increasingly vulnerable to extreme weather events, which encompass a wide range of phenomena,

including droughts, desertification, flooding, and sea level rise. Adenle, Azadi & Arbiol (2015) substantiated this assertion by asserting that the effects of climate change in Africa are not only widespread but are also increasing in both intensity and unpredictability. These impacts are driven by global warming and systemic socio-economic fragilities, such as poverty, infrastructural deficits, and weak institutional preparedness. Two critical climate strategies—adaptation and mitigation—have become the cornerstones of sustainable survival in light of this context. Adaptation, on the other hand, entails "alterations in natural or human systems in response to actual or anticipated climatic stimuli" (Henstra, 2015, p. 497), whereas mitigation concentrates on "actions to reduce or prevent greenhouse gas emissions from human activities" (UNDP, 2024).

Communication remains an underutilised yet crucial innovation in both adaptation and mitigation efforts, despite the extensive research that has concentrated on technological and policy solutions (Rip, 1998; Grubb, 2004; Lybbert & Sumner, 2012). Adenle *et al* (2015) acknowledge this fact when they contend that "technology transfer efforts will fail to achieve scale and social acceptance" in the developing world without strategic communication (p. 269). In essence, communication is not solely a support mechanism; it is a transformative tool that should facilitate the dissemination of knowledge, public participation, stakeholders' engagement, and behavioural change across various sectors and communities.

In the context of Africa, the divide between scientific knowledge and the realities that people face daily is being reduced by innovative communication tools. In light of this, Okesanya, Adekunle, Makinde & Abioye (2024) asserted that African-led climate responses are increasingly utilising participatory storytelling, local language radio programs, mobile Short Message Service notifications, and social media campaigns to inform both rural and urban populations. For instance, the contextualisation of weather forecasts is facilitated by community-based radio in local dialects, and farmers are provided with timely advice on climate-smart agriculture through digital platforms. Daka (2022) effectively articulates the importance of "access to clean technology, but access to information that empowers its use is equally critical" (p. 91).

Additionally, communication has demonstrated its efficacy in influencing both public discourse and policy formulation. Henstra (2015) posits that the success or failure of effective climate adaptation instruments is frequently contingent upon their communication and perception. This renders communication not merely an accessory, but a "core policy tool" that is capable of directing national agendas and garnering support for climate legislation (Henstra, 2015, p. 500).

Therefore, this paper contends that communication is not a peripheral technology, but rather a strategic innovation instrument that has the potential to facilitate significant adaptation and mitigation of climate change in Africa. It commences with a conceptual discussion of communication as a tool of climate governance, which is followed by an examination of innovative communication strategies in Africa, such as grassroots advocacy, digital tools and indigenous knowledge systems. It utilises real-world African case studies to pinpoint persistent obstacles, including language barriers, digital divides,

and limited media access. It concludes with practical suggestions for integrating communication into the climate policy and practice frameworks of Africa.

At its core, the climate crisis is also a communication crisis—one that pertains to equity, access, and urgency. Armani *et al* (2022) correctly assert that "the success of any climate action depends on how well it resonates with the people it seeks to serve" (p. 95). Consequently, Africa must prioritise communication as the primary focus of its climate innovation agenda. The motivation for this study stems from the pressing challenges posed by climate change in Africa. Communities across the continent are facing increasingly severe impacts like rising temperatures, prolonged droughts, destructive floods and expanding desertification. These changes are not just environmental—they threaten people's livelihoods, well-being and the ecosystems they depend on. While efforts to address climate change exist at both global and regional levels, African communities often bear the brunt of its effects due to limited resources, fragile institutions, and insufficient systems to adapt to these challenges.

Theoretical Underpinning

Numerous theories regard communication as a catalyst for development, rather than merely a means of conveying information. However, this investigation is founded on the participatory and development model, Freire's dialogical model, Rogers' diffusion of innovation theory and the media for social change model. The participatory development paradigm explains that communication is a two-way process that influences communities' knowledge through dialogue instead of just sending information. In view of this, Servaes & Malikhao (2020) say that "people must be actively involved in the design and delivery of messages that affect their lives." Also, Mefalopulos (2008) supported this when he asserts that communication should be "horizontal, interactive, and culturally embedded." The dialogical paradigm of Freire (1970) is also utilised in the study. The model posits that communication is essential for climate adaptation and mitigation efforts in an environment where people are sceptical of government institutions due to past failures, as it is a means of co-creation and consciousness-raising. Through participatory learning, radio drama, and narrative, resilience is fostered in fragile contexts such as Somalia through climate education. Additionally, the diffusion of innovations theory (Rogers, 2003) elucidates how society can adopt new climate practices by leveraging trusted networks and media platforms. In practice, it promotes the utilisation of both traditional and digital instruments to establish and maintain a shared understanding of climate change, as well as to facilitate behavioural change that improves the adaptation and mitigation of climate change (Mefalopulos, 2008). These frameworks collectively inform the paper's assertion that communication in Africa must progress beyond awareness-raising to promote engagement, ownership, and sustained climate adaptation and mitigation. Additionally, the media for social change paradigm is equally appropriate for describing communication as a strategy for an effective climate response in Africa. Underpinning this model are the principles of communication for behaviour and social change (CBSC), which extend beyond the linear information model. The focus of the model is on the strategic deployment of communication to engender favourable public

opinion, influence government policy, and induce favourable behavioural changes through the instrument of social media, radio, mobile technology and journalism. This exemplifies the use of investigative climate journalism in Kenya or Malawi and youth digital activism in Uganda (Oniang'o, 2025). Therefore, the effective application of these theories in African contexts to climate discourse will result in the recognition of communication as a transformative force that facilitates the interaction between climate science, indigenous knowledge, and public action to adapt and mitigate climate change.

Understanding Communication as an Instrument

Communication should be understood within the framework of climate change adaptation and mitigation, rather than solely as a method of conveying information. It is a purposefully interactive, participatory and empowering process that changes perception while fostering creativity and resilience. Historically, communication in development and environmental discourse has been defined by the utilisation of mass media, which perceived individuals as audiences susceptible to the influence of the conveyed messages. This method entails the transmission of messages from the expert to the audience in a hierarchical manner (Mefalopulos, 2008, p. xvii). In this framework, the conveyance of a message is a simple, linear and unidirectional procedure (Colombo, 2004). However, this paradigm neglects the complex socio-cultural dynamics and the need for outcome-focused dialogic involvement.

The participatory communication model, characterised by a dialogic approach, contests the linear and restrictive viewpoint by advocating for bottom-up, inclusive procedures wherein communities initially serve as co-creators of knowledge prior to becoming recipients. Paulo Freire asserted, "Dialogue is the encounter in which the collective reflection and action of the participants are directed towards the world that is to be transformed" (Freire, 1970, p. 88). In this context, communication is an innovative tool not just for conveying information but also for cultivating collective agency and critical consciousness.

Everett Rogers' diffusion of innovations theory clarifies the essential function of communication in spreading new ideas and behaviours within a social system. Rogers (2003) emphasised the importance of opinion leaders and change agents in accelerating the adoption of innovations. Influencers pushing renewable energy, community leaders fighting for ecosystem restoration, and farmers adopting climate-smart practices are all contributors to the discourse on climate change. Grubb (2004) noted that "technological innovation alone does not ensure climate resilience" (p. 107). It must be conveyed, contextualised, and acknowledged. Communication is thus a strategic and innovative instrument for climate adaptation and mitigation in Africa.

Moreover, communication functions as a policy tool enabling stakeholder coordination, shaping public discourse, and influencing political agendas. Henstra (2015) observed that adaptation methods' effectiveness often depends on how they are communicated to policymakers and the public. Communication transcends ordinary information conveyance; it is flexible, interconnected, and tactical. Scholars, practitioners, and policymakers must perceive it as a dynamic process of empowerment and engagement to integrate it effectively into Africa's climate response.

Innovative Communication Instruments in Climate Response

Policies, green technologies, and foreign funding are often the first things that come to mind when adapting to and reducing the effects of climate change. Yet the crucial question remains: how are these solutions reaching the people they are meant to serve? In rural areas sensitive to climate change, understanding scientific predictions, policy changes, or new farming techniques requires innovative communication. In such settings, new approaches are not only helpful but essential, serving as active means to engage and empower communities. This calls for attention to modern, digital, indigenous and interactive tools that are reshaping Africa's climate response, one message, one story, one venue at a time.

Mobile Technology

Mobile phones have moved beyond their basic communication function to become indispensable tools for climate adaptation. SMS-based services and voice alerts now deliver agricultural advice, weather forecasts, and early warnings across communities with low literacy or limited internet access. As Daka (2022) observed, mobile platforms are increasingly bridging "the gap between scientific research and farmer behaviour" (p. 90). Tools such as Esoko in Ghana and M-Farm in Kenya allow farmers to receive real-time, personalised information on rainfall patterns, market access, and planting seasons (van Schalkwyk, Young, & Verhulst, n.d.). These services often employ local languages, which increases trust and accessibility. Lybbert and Sumner (2012) emphasise that agricultural innovations succeed in climate-sensitive regions when farmers access "timely and context-specific information" (p. 120). Importantly, many mobile platforms are interactive, allowing farmers to ask questions, seek clarification, and provide feedback. This participatory dynamic transforms user from passive recipients to active decision-makers, aligning with Mefalopulos' (2008) insistence that communication must facilitate dialogue to support collective ownership of development outcomes.

Community Radio

Despite rapid mobile penetration, radio continues to serve as one of Africa's most trusted, affordable, and far-reaching mediums. Its strength lies in its accessibility and localism, offering communication in familiar languages and accents that resonate with audiences. As Chukwunalu (2022) notes, radio speaks a "language that is accessible to all." Although Colombo (2004) critiques radio within linear models of communication, in practice, it increasingly embodies participatory approaches. Across Nigeria, for example, community radio programmes such as Farm Beta and the Ondo State Radiovision forums invite local farmers to share stories, strategies, and coping mechanisms live on-air. Okesanya et al. (2024) argue that such initiatives foster "climate citizenship," encouraging communities to view themselves as active participants in climate response rather than passive observers. The affordability and portability of radios also ensure accessibility in remote regions without electricity or internet coverage, making radio a uniquely inclusive communication tool.

Social Media and Youth-led Digital Activism

Youth-led digital activism represents one of the most dynamic shifts in Africa's climate communication landscape. Platforms such as Twitter (now X), Instagram, Facebook and

YouTube have created new spaces for African voices to challenge, shape, and amplify climate narratives. The Fridays for Future movement demonstrates this impact. In Uganda, Hilda Flavia Nakabuye and peers used social media to galvanise youth engagement, linking local activism with global climate discourse. Nakabuye (2020, p. 212) declared: “Fridays For Future Uganda is paving the way for the development of a robust youth space by promoting activism, climate action, and policy change.” These platforms not only raise awareness but also apply advocacy pressure, strengthen solidarity, and accelerate innovation diffusion, as theorised by Rogers (2003). Henstra (2015) further noted that policy instruments gain legitimacy when framed within persuasive narratives, highlighting the role of influencers and activists in advancing climate agendas.

Indigenous and Oral Communication Systems

Digital innovation alone cannot capture the full communicative ecology of Africa. Indigenous systems, including elders, griots, town criers, festivals and storytelling, remain central to information sharing. These systems endure because they embed messages within cultural frameworks of trust, belonging, and continuity. As Ebine (2019) observes, griots and traditional leaders interpret and relay messages that shape communal action. Mefalopulos (2008) insists that “communication must be culturally embedded to be meaningful” (p. 45), a principle especially critical in climate communication where credibility of the messenger matters as much as the message. Oral narratives, chants, and performances during seasonal transitions not only transmit ecological knowledge but also mobilise conservation practices. When combined with modern media, these traditional systems strengthen locally owned adaptation strategies that are otherwise overlooked by formal climate agencies.

Climate Journalism

Climate journalism is indispensable for linking scientific knowledge, live experiences and policy accountability. It includes mainstream coverage, solutions journalism and investigative reporting. Grubb (2004) observed that “policy and technology constitute but a portion of the solution; public comprehension and advocacy are necessary” (p. 110). Journalists function as watchdogs, educators and agenda-setters. Specialised training in climate science, environmental justice and green policy reporting is crucial for African journalists to shift from episodic disaster coverage to sustained, informed reporting that fosters behavioural change. Initiatives such as InfoNile, a cross-border journalism project, employ data-driven maps to highlight water conflicts, climate migration and environmental degradation (Oniang’o, 2025). Such work has influenced local responses and shaped policy debates. Yet newsroom resource constraints remain, as Adenle *et al* (2015) cautioned, requiring continuous investment to strengthen communication ecosystems.

Communication for Policy and Behavioural Change

Communication serves not only as a means of conveying information but also as a strategic tool for transforming public awareness, guiding political intent, and encouraging

collective behavioural changes in response to intricate issues such as climate change. Servaes & Malikhao (2020) defined communication as the process of sharing knowledge with the objective of achieving a consensus for action, while considering the interests, needs and capacities of all parties involved. In Africa, where climate vulnerabilities intersect with poverty, political instability, and infrastructural shortcomings, effective and innovative communication is both urgent and transformative.

Policy changes often begin with agenda-setting, shaped by communicative actions in media, civil society and politics. Mefalopulos (2008) argued that innovative communication can create shared understanding among decision makers and stakeholders. Thus, communication is not simply informative but a platform for dialogue and deliberation on climate adaptation and mitigation.

Behavioural change, central to adaptation, requires participatory and inclusive communication tailored to the context. Freire's (1970) dialogical model stressed that individuals must act as co-creators of meaning rather than passive recipients. Participatory methods such as community theatre, radio forums, and storytelling have proven effective in rural Africa, where oral traditions remain influential. In Malawi, Zambia and Zimbabwe, radio and television programmes titled "*Our Changing Climate – Our Time to Act!*" promote awareness and action. In Malawi, Chanco FM has become a vital source of information on adaptation and resource management. Its broadcasts have encouraged climate-smart agriculture, with communities adopting drought-resistant crops and diversifying income (Masina, 2023). Such changes stem not from information alone but from dialogue rooted in cultural contexts.

Communication also galvanises collective action when it resonates with identity and urgency. Uganda's Fridays for Future movement under Hilda Flavia Nakabuye illustrates this, combining social media mobilisation with indigenous activism. Nakabuye declared, "We are not merely victims of climate change. We are fighters" (Nakabuye, Nirere & Oladosu, 2020, p. 215). This inspired widespread youth action across East Africa.

Social media further transforms attitudes and norms. Colombo (2004) noted that discursive communication fosters "the construction of meaning through interaction." Platforms such as Twitter, Facebook and WhatsApp now serve as public spheres for dialogue. In Nigeria, youth coalitions and women-led initiatives use digital advocacy to promote sustainability, influencing both policy and household practices (WISE, n.d.; Henry, Rockström & Stern, 2020). To influence climate policy, communication must be dialogic, strategic, evidence-based, and sustained. Journalists are central, connecting local realities to policy outcomes. For example, investigative reports on Lagos flooding by The Guardian linked weak policies to risks, prompting government review and new funding (Adeyeye, 2022).

Communication is thus a strategic lever—vital in shaping policy, inspiring behaviour change, and stimulating civic action. As Mefalopulos (2008) asserts, "without communication, there is no development," a truth central to Africa's climate struggle.

Communication as a Critical Tool for Climate Adaptation and Mitigation in Africa

Communication for climate adaptation and mitigation in Africa is no longer peripheral; it is a fundamental component of climate action, particularly in contexts characterised by

local knowledge systems, institutional constraints and community vulnerability. A comparative analysis of four African case studies—Senegal, Uganda, Kenya, and Somalia—reveals a shared orientation: the deployment of context-sensitive, participatory, and often hybrid communication tools to facilitate engagement, resilience, and behavioural change.

The field report from Guédé Chantier and Thilogne in Senegal illustrates deliberate efforts to integrate climate discourse into local socio-cultural contexts through community radio and agroecological communication. Enda Pronat aligned traditional knowledge with scientific insights via radio broadcasts, on-site demonstrations and peer learning under the Programme d'Appui à la Transition Agroécologique (PATAE). The 2023 PATAE Report states: “the popularisation of practices such as composting, the use of organic inputs, and stone barriers has been made possible through sustained communication between facilitators and producers” (p. 5).

This model reflects the participatory communication paradigm emphasised by Mefalopulos (2008), which prioritises dialogue and inclusion over top-down messaging. The use of local languages, producer groups, and trained facilitators ensured that communications were accessible and co-produced, reinforcing legitimacy and ownership.

In Uganda, youth-led mobilisation has yielded comparable results. The Fridays for Future Uganda movement demonstrates the effectiveness of identity-driven communication. Uganda’s climate communication thrives in digital and activist spaces, contrasting Senegal’s community-based model. Nakabuye and peers declared: “We are not just victims; we are voices for the future,” employing protests and social media narratives to push climate policy into national discourse (Nakabuye, Nirere & Oladosu, 2020, p. 215).

Kenya demonstrates technological mediation through mobile platforms such as M-Farm. Unlike Senegal’s socio-cultural integration or Uganda’s emotion-based mobilisation, Kenya prioritises disseminating functional knowledge for decision-making. Lybbert and Sumner (2012) note that “farmers’ capacity to mitigate climate shocks is substantially enhanced when they receive timely, localised forecasts via SMS” (p. 119). Mobile communication enables anticipatory adaptation. However, as the Senegal case shows, synergy—combining mobiles with radio, group discussions, and face-to-face sessions—is critical to impact (PATAE Report, 2023).

Somalia highlights the role of conflict-sensitive communication. Community radio, storytelling, and radio dramas embed environmental themes within peacebuilding narratives. These strategies address mistrust, insecurity and low literacy. The BRCiS programme overcame structural obstacles by using culturally relevant stories and trusted local voices, enabling climate communication to serve as both environmental education and social repair (Freire, 1970; Colombo, 2004).

A clear pattern emerges: effective climate communication in Africa is multimodal, culturally adaptive, and rooted in participation. Senegal exemplifies agroecological knowledge transfer; Uganda mobilises youth consciousness; Kenya integrates technology; and Somalia demonstrates healing capabilities in fragile contexts.

Yet deficiencies remain. Institutional support and policy coherence are inconsistent. In Senegal, “many community facilitators still operate without formal pedagogical tools or stable funding” (PATAE Report, 2023, p. 6). In Uganda, youth

campaigns often lack institutional channels for sustained influence. As Adenle *et al* (2015) argue, “technological and policy innovations must be scaled through dynamic, well-supported communication networks” (p. 265).

Challenges to Effective Climate Communication in Africa

Despite recognition of communication as critical, multiple barriers undermine its potential. A major challenge is the absence of established communication strategies in national climate policies. The Senegal field report notes the lack of frameworks regulating communication in climate-sensitive sectors such as agriculture and environmental governance (PATAE, 2023, p. 6). Without direction, initiatives risk being fragmented and dependent on donor projects.

Grassroots efforts are also weakened by limited training. Many facilitators and educators lack updated knowledge and pedagogical resources. Mefalopulos (2008) emphasised that “capacity building is essential for transforming communication into an empowering process” (p. 32). In Senegal, facilitators have expressed frustration over inadequate support (PATAE, 2023).

Language diversity and technological exclusion pose further obstacles. Radios and mobiles are not universally accessible, especially for marginalised groups or the elderly. The frequent use of French or English marginalises indigenous speakers. Colombo (2004) stressed that “communication is meaningful only when messages are in alignment with the lived experiences of individuals.”

In fragile states like Somalia, insecurity and political instability impede climate messaging. Radio dramas under the BRCiS programme must contend with misinformation, ethnic tensions, and low trust, making conflict-sensitive validation essential (Freire, 1970). Weak media engagement and limited funding persist. Many journalists lack training in environmental reporting and climate desks in newsrooms are rare (Oniang’o, 2025). Without consistent investment, the media cannot fulfil its educational and watchdog roles. Collectively, these obstacles indicate that climate communication must be integrated, culturally informed, and well supported to drive real behavioural and policy transformation.

Conclusion

Climate change remains one of the most pressing issues confronting Africa, yet the way it is discussed and who communicates are as important as the content itself. This investigation has shown the potential of communication to transform realities when effectively executed. From community radio in Senegal aiding farmers’ agroecological practices, to youth activists in Uganda and mobile alerts guiding Kenyan farmers, communication is shaping how people comprehend, respond to, and prepare for climate realities. However, challenges persist. Communication is often underfunded, poorly organised, or disconnected from those most affected. Language barriers, inadequate training, and fragile institutions further diminish its impact. Looking ahead, Africa requires communication systems that are inclusive, creative, and people-centred—empowering communities, informing decision-makers and linking local knowledge with science. Beyond dissemination, communication must stimulate action and co-creation. The continent’s climate resilience may depend on the strength of its voices to not only warn but also inspire change. Thus, a primary goal of national climate policies should be

the integration of communication techniques, the provision of specific funds, and the enhancement of capability. As a result, communication will be an integral part of both adaptation and mitigation strategies, rather than an afterthought. Secondly, organisations working to improve climate communication should be recognised and supported by governments and NGOs. These individuals should be trained to effectively engage communities and possess a solid grasp of scientific concepts. Gaining credibility and making an influence, especially at the grassroots level, will be made easier with this dual competency. Also, technology should be used inclusively, making sure that digital advances and mobile apps are easy to use, accessible and listen to local opinions. One way to break down geographical and generational boundaries is to combine traditional and modern platforms.

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